

Workflow for Implementing Energy Analysis Across a BIM Design Lifecycle

SARA ANTUNES

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Abstract

The continuum growth of energy consumption, increasing CO₂ emissions and utilisation of natural resources are intrinsically connected to the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry. To mitigate this negative outcome and provide a more sustainable approach to construction, this thesis aims to develop a structured energy analysis workflow applicable across the design process in an architectural and engineering design company. Central to this workflow is integrating energy analysis in the conceptual design phase and milestones throughout the design development stage, allowing for continuous evaluation of whether the project aligns with its predetermined energy efficiency objectives.

The thesis addressed the following questions: How can energy analysis be integrated into the entire design lifecycle – from the pre-design to the detailed phase- and what are the challenges of applying energy analysis in design phases?

To achieve this, the research begins with a comprehensive literature review, examining both theoretical frameworks and practical implementations adopted by other companies. Key

aspects explored include methods for defining energy goals within an organisation, translating these objectives into measurable variables for energy analysis, and strategies for conducting energy analysis at each phase of the design process.

Ultimately, the culmination of this research yielded a tested workflow, refined through practical application in a selected project of the company, which holds potential applicability across various design firms.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/533X5ipzJKM>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13899075